

PRECANCEROUS DISEASES OF THE STOMACH

Elyorbek Namozov Ilhom o'g'li

Faculty of Medicine, International University of Asia, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13982563>

Abstract. *Precancerous conditions of the stomach are changes to stomach cells that make them more likely to develop into cancer. These conditions are not yet cancer. But if they aren't treated, there is a chance that these abnormal changes may become stomach cancer.*

Keywords: *The most common factors for the development of stomach cancer, Chronic atrophic gastritis, Polyps and polyposis of the stomach, Gastric ulcer is considered a precancerous disease.*

ПРЕДРАКОВЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ЖЕЛУДКА

Аннотация. *Предраковые состояния желудка — это изменения в клетках желудка, которые повышают вероятность их развития в рак. Эти состояния еще не являются раком. Но если их не лечить, есть вероятность, что эти аномальные изменения могут стать раком желудка.*

Ключевые слова: *Наиболее распространенные факторы развития рака желудка, Хронический атрофический гастрит, Полипы и полипоз желудка, Язва желудка считается предраковым заболеванием.*

A necessary condition for the occurrence of gastric cancer is considered to be accelerated division of epithelial cells of the gastric mucosa. With the development of a tumor process, the epithelium of the gastric mucosa changes in a certain sequence: in the normal epithelium, cells first begin to divide more actively, and then atypical cells appear. Chronic inflammation of the gastric mucosa is the main predisposing factor for the development of gastric cancer.

The most common factors for the development of stomach cancer are:

- 1) Helicobacter pylori infection
- 2) Nature and composition of food, alcohol
- 3) Smoking
- 4) Age, sex and hereditary factors (the average age of patients is 50-60 years, stomach cancer occurs twice as often in men than in women).

Background precancerous diseases of the stomach:

Chronic atrophic gastritis. With this disease, in the gastric mucosa, along with atrophy, areas of pronounced proliferation and dysplasia of epithelial cells are often found. In many

patients, the process is accompanied by the growth of epithelium in the stomach, characteristic of the intestines (intestinal metaplasia).

Polyps and polyposis of the stomach. Polyps look like round formations protruding into the lumen of the stomach, located on a thin stalk or a wide base. Depending on the microscopic structure, there are several types of stomach polyps

Gastric ulcer is considered a precancerous disease. There are serious reasons for this, since when examined in the circumference of the ulcer, atypical restructuring of the epithelium is often detected. The pathogenesis of cancer in gastric ulcers is not completely clear

Atrophic gastritis of the resected stomach. The natural outcome of gastric resection is a decrease in the acidity of gastric juice and the reflux of bile into the stump of the stomach. This leads to the development of chronic gastritis in the gastric stump, which is often accompanied by dysplasia and intestinal metaplasia of the epithelium.

REFERENCES

1. Saodat, A., Vohid, A., Ravshan, N., & Shamshod, A. (2020). MRI study in patients with idiopathic coxarthrosis of the hip joint. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2), 410-415.
2. Axmedov, S. J. (2023). EFFECTS OF THE DRUG MILDRONATE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(20), 40-59.
3. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). ASCORBIC ACID: ITS ROLE IN IMMUNE SYSTEM, CHRONIC INFLAMMATION DISEASES AND ON THE ANTIOXIDANT EFFECTS. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(11), 57-60.
4. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THIOTRIAZOLINE IN THE ORGANISM. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 9(5), 152-155.
5. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). HEPTRAL IS USED IN LIVER DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 35(3), 76-78.
6. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). EFFECT OF TIVORTIN ON CARDIOMYOCYTE CELLS AND ITS ROLE IN MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 42, 255-257.
7. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF CITICOLINE. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(1), 1-4.

8. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF TRIMETAZIDINE IN ISCHEMIC CARDIOMYOPATHY. *Journal of new century innovations*, 44(2), 3-8.
9. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ВСЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИМУДОН. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 39-43.
10. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE EFFECT OF THE HEPARIN DRUG. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 34-38.
11. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF GLUCOCORTICOSTEROIDS IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 29-33.
12. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РОЛЬ ИНТЕЛЛАНОВОГО СИРОПА И ЦИАНОКОБАЛАМИНА В УЛУЧШЕНИИ ПАМЯТИ. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 44-48.
13. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). TREATMENT OF POLYNEUROPATHY WITH BERLITHION. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 201-209.
14. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF ASCORIL IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 191-200.
15. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ARTOXAN. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 182-190.
16. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF RENGALIN IN CHRONIC BRONCHITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 116-123.
17. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF ALMAGEL DRUG IN GASTRIC AND DUODENAL WOUND DISEASE. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 173-181.
18. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF CODELAK BRONCHO SYRUP IN CHILDREN'S PRACTICE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 109-115.
19. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE AEVIT DRUG EFFECT. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 124-132.
20. Ilhom o'g'li, E. N. (2024). WAYS TO PREVENT FUTURE CONSEQUENCES OF RECTAL CANCER. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(9), 302-305